

IPBES TCA Chapter 3. Review of knowledge on theories and frameworks of transformative change / IPBES transformative change assessment (3.1)

Survey questions to chapter 3 authors

1. Theories/Frameworks (T&F): Provide a short name
2. Description of the T&F in 200 words. Think text book description
 - 2.1. Expressed assumptions or ontologies / why are they proposed (incl. political aspects, worldviews)
 - 2.2. Do they include ILK? What knowledge systems and disciplines are they based on?
 - 2.3. What is the T&F trying to tackle or solve? What is its underlying goal?
3. Key references showing how this T&F contributes to a better understanding of transformative change
4. Is this a theory to describe an emergent or an intentional transformative process, or a combination?
 - 4.1. Is there a difference between initiating or steering a change?
 - 4.2. Is this T&F proposing predominantly top-down or bottom up approaches? Are combinations possible?
5. What are the epistemologies of this T&F?
 - 5.1. What are the central assumptions or ontologies of behaviour under this T&F?
 - 5.2. How do these assumptions and ontologies relate to nature?
6. How this T&F addresses cultural and social norms, values, worldviews, beliefs and paradigms?
7. How transformative change occurs (narrative of process how it happens)?
 - 7.1. Objective/vision of the transformation (transformation towards which vision)
 - 7.2. Indirect drivers of change / moderating factors (Governance; Institutions; human preferences; market structure; inequalities)
 - 7.3. Direct drivers of change (methods; Instruments; tools; policies; resources (inputs))
 - 7.4. What are the causal linkages/relationships - and feedbacks - among indirect and direct drivers?
8. How this T&F addresses Agency and Power?
 - 8.1. Who/which are the Agents of Change?
 - 8.2. Are there Power differentials across the scales and sectors?
 - 8.3. How does this T&F approach power?
9. At what scales does this T&F contribute to transformative change?
 - 9.1. Temporal scale (short, medium, long term)
 - 9.2. Spatial scale (local, regional, country, global)
 - 9.3. Societal scale (individual or personal/ community or collective/ society)
 - 9.4. Any other relevant scale?
10. Is this T&F used to understand transformative change in a particular system or subsystem (e.g. energy system, food system, financial, individuals)?
 - 10.1. Target audience
11. Outcomes
 - 11.1. Implications on cultural and social norms, values, worldviews, beliefs and paradigm
 - 11.2. Policy implications
 - 11.3. Potential indicators of change

- 11.4. Does this T&F address the SDGs? Which ones?
 - 11.5. Relevance to the transformation we want/need as outlined in Ch 1
 - 11.6. Does this T&F address biodiversity targets? Which ones?
 - 11.7. Does this T&F address ecosystem services and wellbeing? Which services? Which wellbeing aspects?
 - 11.8. Does this T&F address human/nature relationships? How?
12. General Comments